

Recent TipESM Activities

TipESM policy briefing: Human Rights and Climate Tipping Points

On 6 March 2026 TipESM delivered a policy briefing focused on human rights and climate tipping points. The event took place in Geneva, Switzerland, at the 61st session of the UN Human Rights Council. Access the presentations delivered by TipESM researchers:

- [Global climate tipping points: What are they and what could they mean?](#)
- [The Amazon: A potential tipping point for the Earth's climate system](#)
- [Do we need a legal framework for loss of habitability due to extreme heat?](#)

Publication: The future for Tour De France and other outdoor summer sports

In February the article 'The future of European outdoor summer sports through the lens of 50 years of the Tour de France' was published in Scientific Reports with Ivana Cvijanovic as lead author.

"In a way, we can say that it is an extremely fortunate race, but with record-breaking heatwaves becoming more frequent, it is only a matter of time before the Tour encounters extreme heat stress days that will test the existing safety protocols" Ivana explains.

You can read the Carbon Brief coverage of the interesting study [here](#).

Or access the publication [here](#).

Recent TipESM Activities

TipESM at the TIPMIP General Assembly 2026 in Tokyo

TipESM was well represented at the TIPMIP General Assembly, held at the University of Tokyo, Japan, from 4–6 March. The assembly brought together researchers to discuss tipping likelihood, the impacts of tipping events, and tipping interactions – with many talks and discussions on climate irreversibility in idealized overshoot scenario simulations. A bunch of TipESM researchers attended the assembly, contributing with talks and posters. See [the list of contributions on our webpage](#).

Deliverable 1.2: Triggering tipping events in coupled Earth System Models

Our newest deliverable on triggering tipping events in coupled Earth System Models is now available on [zenodo](#).

This report details the experiment protocols for the TipESM forced simulations and the methods to deliberately induce tipping events in these simulations. It describes the methodologies for triggering tipping events in three major tipping elements of the Earth system, the Atlantic Meridional Overturning Circulation (AMOC), the Amazon tropical forest and the Antarctic ice shelves.

Publication: Tipping dynamics of the AMOC

The protocol paper for the TipESM_forced simulations related to AMOC is now [available here](#) (open for discussion and under review in Geoscientific Model Development) with Didier Swingedouw as lead author. The paper describes the experimental protocol for a set of coordinated simulations involving oceanic surface freshwater flux perturbations, conducted as part of the international Tipping Points Modelling Intercomparison Project (TIPMIP).

TipESM at EGU26

The annual EGU General Assembly will take place on 3 - 8 May 2026 in Vienna. TipESM will be strongly represented at the event:

- Extreme heat: characterization, drivers, prediction and impacts in a warming climate - session co-convened by Ivana Cvijanovic
- Reversible Atlantic overturning despite continued Greenland Ice Sheet melt in global climate overshoot scenarios – Oral presentation by Chuncheng Guo
- Impacts of freshwater fluxes on ice shelves tipping points in UKESM – Oral presentation by Dieu Hoang
- Sahara and boreal forests natural vegetation: from mid-Holocene to future – Poster by Charline Ragon
- Climate and carbon cycle responses to a 21st century AMOC collapse under a 2°C stabilization pathway - Oral presentation by Thomas Frölicher
- Disparities in recovery capacity amplify inequality under consecutive extreme events - Oral presentation by Inga Sauer

TipESM - OptimESM Annual Meeting 2026 in Copenhagen

The annual TipESM and OptimESM meeting will take place on on at the Danish Meteorological Institute (DMI) in Copenhagen, Denmark on June 1-4 2026. The OptimESM annual meeting will be on June 1, while the joint meeting is June 2-3 and the TipESM annual meeting on June 4.

The annual meeting will also feature an outreach event on June 2nd on the latest tipping point science. Leading climate researchers will share key findings on tipping point mechanisms and connections, the risks they pose, and their potential impacts on society and ecosystems.